

Dismantling Sociocultural Barriers: Pakistan's Growing Women Entrepreneurship through Digital Spaces

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ABSTRACT: Entrepreneurship is a profession, where men have historically held a disproportionate amount of power for being the sole performers in that role. Same is the case of Pakistan, the establishment of clear limits on one's work area in accordance with one's gender role and responsibilities, is heavily influenced by cultural norms and values. The ethnographic study was carried out in two urban centers Islamabad the Capital of Pakistan and Rawalpindi. A purposive sample of hundred and twenty-six women entrepreneurs from the above locale was selected for the study. The selected participants were engaged in entrepreneurship through digital platforms either fully or partially. The study findings projected that digital literacy as enabler for women to participate in areas of life where they have previously been excluded. The growing digitalization has brought changes which have influenced every aspect of their life. They gained digital and business skills that contributed to the cultural transformation, leading to the increase of female entrepreneurs within society. They had been an influential force in mentoring other women for digital inclusion and for growth of their business. The socio-cultural contexts create challenges due to gender inequalities, limited knowledge, mobility limitations which were managed by the digital efficacy of women entrepreneurs. Digital skills for networking, delivering, mobility and marketing were utilized to handle previously held cultural barriers.

Key words: Digital humanism, Women entrepreneurs, Cultural challenges, Digital ethnography.

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1. Introduction

Being an entrepreneur is often defined as persons who are innovative, risk-takers, and capable of capitalizing on opportunities, have traditionally propelled economic progress. Nonetheless, throughout time, it has become obvious that entrepreneurs contribute to economic growth. Women's participation and engagement in entrepreneurial efforts has increased in recent decades. However, women's potential contributions cannot be disregarded. that women account for at least half of the population in most countries, the

overall degree of poverty among them has a considerable impact on the economy of any country. Women-owned businesses are uncommon in low-income nations such as Pakistan, where the socio-cultural framework favours males in public spaces and women in domestic settings.

The findings of research and prior studies have led to seeing the entrepreneurial phenomenon in masculine terms and associating it with male characteristics such as risk-taking, aggression, and competitiveness, also known as hegemonic masculinity (Bruni, Poggio, & Gherardi, 2004). The literature indicates that a conception of entrepreneurship based on socially constructed masculine stereotypes continues to be one of the main obstacles, even in the face of regulatory support to increase women's involvement in venture development (Ahl, 2006).

Furthermore, a potential to have a more thorough and contextual understanding of women entrepreneurs has been lost as a result of the gender blindness approach (Welter & Smallbone, 2010). Studying female entrepreneurs is essential to understanding their views on entrepreneurship and how they define success in this industry. Creating new definitions of entrepreneurship that take contextual factors like gender inequality and how it influences the entrepreneurial growth is crucial to be accounted for a complete understanding.

Understanding infrastructural systems and how they relate to social and cultural life is made easier with the lens of digital humanism and of digital anthropology (Hine C. , 2015; Helsper, 2009; Henry, Foss, & Ahl, 2016). If we want to continue to understand how technology affects people's lives in the actual world, digital anthropology is essential. The field of digital anthropology encompasses the current study. "The digital humanism " is expressed in prosperous future achievements, frightful fears and inflated visions that incorporates impact technical progress, policymaking, and investment decisions. The understanding of this topic is currently being advanced by the new research on digital infrastructures, as demonstrated by the works (Marlow & McAdam, 2012; Ahmad, Rafiq, & Ahmad, 2018; Maqbool, Parveen, & Yousuf, 2021) . This study searched on digital humanism to show how the cultural context influenced women's participation in digital technologies, which produced new job opportunities.

Research questions

- What societal attitudes and perceptions toward women entrepreneurs exist, and how do they shape women's experiences in business?
- How do women navigate socio-cultural constraints to establish and sustain their businesses?

Objective

To explore the socio-cultural factors influencing women's entrepreneurship in Pakistan and to identify the key barriers and enablers in their entrepreneurial journeys.

2. Literature Review

Nowadays, there is a clear and considerable trend towards women being self-employed and business owners. The trend had been found on increase in the beginning of this century in the developed regions. Numerous research statistics, on the other hand, give a good idea of the levels of female entrepreneurship in various countries (Anderson & Gaddefors, 2016; Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2021). Statistics from extensive research on women's entrepreneurship in the United States and Canada show that enterprises owned and operated by females in the United States account for 28% of the 23 million firms (or 6.4 million) and employ 9.2 million people. This is equivalent to 9% of all private sector employment (World Bank, 2011). Unfortunately, there are very little statistics and figures about female entrepreneurship in the literature from the underdeveloped regions around the globe. This is partly because most countries and regions lack official statistics on the gender of business owners and that many businesses are not registered according to their industry, location, and size (Butler, 2004). This makes difficult in determining the actual ratio of female entrepreneurship and the differences between nations and regions.

Women's entrepreneurial endeavours, whether they take place in the informal or formal sectors, in small or medium-sized production activities, or both, have beneficial social effects on both the women who engage in them and the society in which they live (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2021). Women are "drawn" to entrepreneurship not just by the prospect of financial gain, but also by the freedom to pursue a work-life balance (Parveen & Junaid, 2019). The ability of female entrepreneurs to prioritise both work and family life has been identified as one of their most admirable traits. The socio-cultural norms and family expectations generate significant workload and creates challenging environment for them to peruse entrepreneurship. The work-life balance challenges identified in the early research, points significantly that it affects the motivations and capacities of women in small business initiatives when compared to their male counterparts (Carter & Marlow, 2007; Anzak & Sultana, 2020). Research also found that the dynamic between men and women business owners differed geographically and demographically especially for women entrepreneurs in regions like Saudi Arabia, Madagascar, Qatar, and Brazil. The countries with the lowest rates of female entrepreneurs include Pakistan, Japan, North Macedonia, and Norway (A & Tuffley, 2014; A & J, 2017; Brodman & Berazneva, 2007).

Pakistani culture is deeply rooted in the patriarchal system that promotes gender differences in every walk of life (Muhammad, Ximei, Saqib, & Beutell, 2021). In Pakistan, there are always more men than women employed in each profession. Women participation compared to men in agricultural work account for the highest percentage 38%, followed by professionals 30% and elementary unskilled employees 21% (UN Women, 2021). Global rankings have also shown gender disparities in Pakistan. Pakistan is ranked 151st out of 153 nations in the worldwide gender parity report published by the World Economic Forum (World Economic Forum, 2020). Pakistan was ranked 76th out of 100 nations in The Economist's Inclusive Internet Index, with the largest gender gaps in access to the internet and mobile devices (The Economist, 2020).

Social and cultural norms, on the one hand, and family issues, on the other, were certainly create challenging environment for female entrepreneurs in patriarchal countries (Poggesi, Mari, & De Vita, 2016). As a result, Roomi et al. (Roomi, Rehman, & Henry, 2018) contend that women's entrepreneurial career choices are shaped by a complex interplay of socio-cultural factors. Furthermore, socio-cultural factors influence the level of entrepreneurial activity in each time and place (Khan, Salamzadeh, Shah, & Hussain, 2020). It includes lack of access to and control over resources, fewer educational opportunities, weaker family support, lack of self-actualization, and lack of entrepreneurial orientation had been contributing to the less participation among women in the entrepreneurship (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

3. Significance of the Study

This research is significant for many reasons, foremost contribution of empirical research is to dispel intuitions by examining the phenomenon in the context. Despite the widespread acceptance of the need to comprehend effective entrepreneurial behaviors that promote desirable economic and development outcomes, research into women's entrepreneurship in new ventures is less prominent in underdeveloped regions of the world. By providing an understanding of how women entrepreneurs are operating in the Pakistani context, this study may help to close the knowledge gap exists in literature. Their successes and methods for overcoming contextual barriers were crucial components of their success because they foster creativity.

It generates the information on a regional overview of the difficulties and obstacles that women entrepreneurs were faced with, when they want to establish and grow their own business, must overcome. Such data will be useful for policymakers to consider when developing new initiatives to support the growth of women entrepreneurs. By emphasizing successes, founder-CEOs of new businesses with genuine leadership behaviors foster trust, boosting emotional security and creativity among women entrepreneurs.

4. Methodology

The current study utilized digital ethnography for the research. Ethnographic inquiry in the digital realm is a way to learn more about what digital things mean and how they are connected to technology, as well as the cultural experiences that are made possible by the digital medium (Hine C. , 2000). The research was conducted in the Rawalpindi and Islamabad the capital city in Pakistan. 126 women entrepreneurs were selected for the study through purposive sampling. The data was collected with the help of participant observations, three focus group discussions and fifty-one in-depth interviews. Case studies were collected during the field work to explore the cultural norms and its implications on the entrepreneurial ventures carried out by the women entrepreneurs with the digital technology incorporation.

5. Findings and Discussion

Despite women entrepreneur's substantial contributions to the industry, the current study identified some obstacles and difficulties experienced by female entrepreneurs in Pakistan. By looking at these barriers, this study aims to clarify the elements that can make it more difficult for Pakistani women entrepreneurs to succeed. Women entrepreneurs are underrepresented in emerging economies, which has led to their important contributions to attempts to reduce poverty and increase GDP going unacknowledged (Khan I. , 2014). The complex relationships that arise from the interaction of sociocultural elements, religious convictions, and family structures were examined in this study. A small number of previous research have also clarified how important context is in understanding the behaviour of female entrepreneurs and how their success was significantly impacted by the cultural norms (Dinar, 2020; Noor, Isa, & Nor, 2021; Rehman & Azam Roomi, 2012).

Pakistan, a patriarchal country, used gender-based approaches to provide males and females with selective social positions, education, and career opportunities. Women in Pakistan experience considerable difficulties as a result of societal gender bias. Their limited decision-making power in both the familial and communal realms was linked to their subjugation to the male leaders of the household, as well as their limited mobility, which hampered their capacity to access necessary services. Purdah norms and mobility constraints being enforced were commonly observed during fieldwork, limiting their access to opportunities in public domains. They were seen to be engaged in vocations that allowed them to contact with ladies. Similarly, the entrepreneur/

Table 1: Barriers to Women Entrepreneurship

Barriers to their growth	N	Percentage %
No barriers at all	25	19.8
Financial and economic challenges	37	29.4
Social and familial acceptance	31	24.6
Employees, management, and regulations	33	26.2
Grand Total	126	100

The roles that are socially assigned for women provide the basis for discriminatory practices and prevent women from fully participating in society. Women's chances for both professional and personal growth are severely limited by social norms and marginalization, which prevent them from engaging in economic activities (UN Women, 2018). Table 1, below is listing for the barriers these respondents accounted for the startup and growth of their entrepreneurship. The most significant challenge and for which 29.4 % entrepreneurs talked about was the economic and financial means they needed for their ventures, but it was another significant finding that almost equal number of respondents 24.6% accounted for the society and family attitude in acceptance of doing entrepreneurship. However, over 20% reported no encounters with impediments. They had encountered occasional impediments, such as infrastructure, in which they needed to buy raw materials from outside countries and had to use payment methods that were not available, but they had networked for this payment method.

Access to Finance:

Financial challenges have long been recognized as a substantial impediment to entrepreneurial ambition and success. This barrier was seen to have a negative impact on women-owned businesses. According to research findings, the majority of women rely mostly on personal resources and traditional sources of financing, such as aid from a close family member or acquaintance. Obtaining financial assistance from the bank in the form of loans or from angel investors has institutional and theological constraints. The respondents explained the many reasons they regularly encountered when acquiring money. They were unable to take advantage of the prospects because of a considerably weaker credit history resulting from irregular working histories, lower compensation, and restricted assets. They also had cultural influences on loan benefits, and they occasionally used the fear of business failure to encourage people to take out bank loans. They are concerned that if they lose money in business, they will struggle to repay the debt. While elaborating on the experience of a friend the respondent informed about her precautionary behaviour.

Respondent 70 stated, "I do not wish to take a loan; I will grow insha Allah via my hard work. A friend who took out a loan to start a retail business experienced a significant loss owing to a fraudster. She was unable to contact him, lost money, and faced criticism from her family for her inefficiency. She was also responsible for loan repayment. "Na baba na (no no), I will avoid getting into such a situation."

Access to the finance and financial opportunities also is a challenging situation for the women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. It was for many reasons given by the entrepreneurs which includes lack of awareness and legal formalities to gain funds and financial support from microfinance institutions or banks. Microfinance institutions in Pakistan have requirement that female clients must provide two male guarantors (WorldBank, 2018) so it becomes a barrier for many of the women to reach out financial opportunities. Despite having high scores in economic achievements entrepreneurship indicators for women worldwide still face many practical and financial barriers for becoming successful entrepreneurs (Worldbank, 2022). The lack of access to finance presents a significant obstacle, resulting in an estimated \$1.7 trillion of unfulfilled requests for 30 credits (International Finance Corporation, 2017). The findings of this study also discovered that while the government had introduced several incentives to help small enterprises, the benefits had not reached a bigger number of women entrepreneurs. The research also revealed that many women visited the bank for loans, but they need male guarantor to sign the forms, and the additional paperwork were so lengthy that they abandoned their plans to apply. One of the Respondent criticized the opportunistic female entrepreneurs in her group, saying,

"Only sharp and approachable have access to such benefits not like us."

Another respondent, a member of the chamber house told upon highlighting the need of financial support women entrepreneurs significant challenge in their startup and growth phase. She said "We are planning to meet our mayor in Islamabad to make him go to the ministry of small and medium enterprises and convince them to announce for some financial support to the women entrepreneurs."

Financial limitations' detrimental effects on business endeavours, particularly those headed by women, have drawn a lot of attention and academic study. This research article accounts on how important it is to overcome the obstacles presented by financial issues to empower women in business and create an atmosphere that is favourable for the growth of entrepreneurship. According to the study's findings, a sizable fraction of women relies mostly on their own savings and traditional funding sources, like financial support from close relatives or reliable friends. This dependence on individual savings and conventional financing sources demonstrates the prevalent financial trends among women. Through an analysis of women's financial behaviour, this study illuminates the elements that impact their decision-making regarding access to fundings.

The acquisition of financial aid, whether in the form of loans from banks or through incubation centers, is subject to certain structural and religious limitations. These limitations can impact the accessibility and availability of financial resources for individuals and businesses seeking assistance. It is crucial to understand and analyze these limitations to comprehend the potential challenges and constraints that may arise in the process of obtaining financial aid. The data analysis shed light on various factors that influence the distribution and allocation of financial resources, thereby enabling us to make informed decisions and navigate the financial landscape more effectively.

One of the respondents expressed the challenge she encountered in accessing financial opportunities, which was a limitation for many as the data showed the number of registered businesses was low in this study. It highlights the limitation imposed by the absence of official registration for their business. Consequently, they found themselves ineligible to receive financial support from the government, leaving them uncertain about alternative sources of funding, despite their commendable efforts in their entrepreneurial endeavors.

1. Fear of Loss in Business:

Associated with the above challenge that accounts to the financial capital as an important requirement towards the journey of entrepreneurship the fear of loss of this capital is another obstacle with which these entrepreneurs got stuck up. Fear of loss in the business is one big obstacle in startups and sustainability of entrepreneurship. Families and friends do not support the women business in financial capacity because the concept of businesswomen is not very familiar in Pakistani society.

Every business had been growing up with the element of profit and loss but women in entrepreneurship ecosystem are stuck up with this obstacle more frequently because of their low financial resources and support they need if unfortunately, they come across any loss. Many of the respondents have been discouraged by their friends and family to invest their savings in startup business. This was more prominently where they do not have any closer or extended family member engaged in business activity.

Respondent 73 said "I've experienced a constant alarm of demoralization from my family, who made it abundantly clear that they believed my business was destined for failure. I will not succeed . . . in our society male gets chance to try but females are not even allowed to try so after hard time of convincing their parents and family if they try to start a

business now they have another burden of making it a success one way or other because otherwise she will be made fun of by the family members and they will say we already knew you are not capable and you will ruin the assets. Karoobar[business] is not a child's play".

So, to stand by alone in entrepreneurial ecosystem was strange for some of the research respondents as mentioned during their interview. Field observations and informal conversations build insights that women entrepreneurs looked for a supportive structure to take the risk in the business investments, they seek advice from the other entrepreneurs and do take out "Sadaqa[charity] in the name of Allah" as a religious ritual to seek blessings of the supernatural. They were also looking forward to family support and it was mostly found unavailable, so their investments were smaller and mostly generated through savings. Society in general fears it risky to invest in the female ventures as their success was seen doubtful and risky. This was the prevailing perception among all the respondents of the study. This prevailing ambiguity about women as an unsustainable entrepreneur limits their opportunities of growth and also limits their pool of investors unless they prove with few initial years of success. Either they had this fear developed by hearing the stories of losses from their fellow entrepreneurs or partly because the family support to their initiative was not present.

A respondent marked for the critique and ridiculed they had to face if bear the loss, "aur no sunao" and you do not listen. So, on one end I had to bear the loss and other end face the critique for not listening to them and their warnings about loss in business." So in most of the cases that was a loss of financial capital, and the lack of social support also decreases the hopes to take further risks and bring innovations in the business.

Another respondent said that; "Linguistic terminology "businessman" generated the perceptions held by the society that male gender to be the right person for this professional line. Even if the women at their own savings able to startup their entrepreneurship they were warned to get ready to bear the loss instead of encouraging or wishing her Goodluck with her endeavors. Such an investment is seen by them as a "loss of money" or "putting money in drain".

The Chamber house meetings and after Covid-19 the Zoom meetups were found to be the strategies to identify the solutions for their mental and financial losses they had to bear in their journey of growth. Shch meetings were seen a relieving place where they share their fears about entrepreneurial venture, about launching new ideas and the grief of their losses. They were not challenged but rather supported by this social capital in these venues by giving their examples of risk they took in the past and got failed, then how they managed it. They were told by the key informants of my research that it is part and parcel of their professional life, and they get the family support very less on these arears.

2. Cultural Norms and Contextual Limitations:

Pakistani women compared to western women face more challenges to get involved in entrepreneurial fields. These challenges are mostly due to cultural constraints, less education, less financial assets in their possession and even if there is an opportunity there will be a lot of gender-based discrimination through prevailing prejudices in the Pakistani society. Even if a woman goes out to start her own business in Pakistan, she faces a lot

more problem than men simply because of their gender. Present study found that gender undermines their legitimacy and dealing with these gender challenges in day-to-day adds to their growth and sustainability. Respondent told, "I had a craze of calligraphy, and it was not permissible to go outside the home to learn calligraphy. Alhamdulillah our family is so religious - yaha koi females teach nai karti and males kay pas sikhnay ki ijazt nai thi (so in our context female teachers of calligraphy are not available and cannot go to males for learning because not permitted for this), then Allah made a way to learn online. I took 15 classes and then started my work."

Another respondent said, "I had limited opportunities to explore because of purda and mobility restrictions being practiced in her family'.

It is a challenging obstacle to her growth, yet the digital literacy enabled her to groom her dream through online space and after exploration she adopted the path to start her business. So, like many other respondents who were challenged by the cultural norms made their way through digital media and created their online ventures. It's important to note that females are not inherently less educated or well-trained, but they had lower self-worth and lower expectations found in the cultural context about women owning businesses in general (Ahmet & Selcen, 2019).

In general, women in Pakistan face numerous challenges in carrying out and managing their businesses. Household duties, infant care, and serving elderly members in the family were constant expectations placed on these women. Most women had internalized their parental and familial responsibilities. Many provided examples of other employed women in their society had successfully balanced labor and domestic duties with the support full-time workers as helpers. Many respondents in this study had also resigned from their previous jobs and went into entrepreneurship in hopes of improved time management with their families and work. They were able to balance their family responsibilities while also dedicating time to their own personal growth and economic advancement.

3. Patriarchal Society and Subordinate Position of Women:

The significance of the social expectations placed upon female entrepreneurs is further underscored by their alignment with the previously established findings in the literature review, specifically pertaining to the influence of patriarchal culture. This study found patriarchal structure manifests itself in various aspects of life, including family dynamics, education, employment opportunities, and decision-making processes. This power imbalance is deeply rooted in cultural norms, traditions, and societal expectations. Consequently, women often face limited agency, reduced access to resources, and restricted participation in public spheres. Research also found age-based power dynamic prevalent and evident in the family to establish the patriarchal norms. The normative restrictions are enforced within familial contexts, primarily by parents and siblings, particularly by male individuals.

In the context of Pakistani society, this hierarchical arrangement is evident, with males occupying a position of greater power than females, thereby establishing a

patriarchal system. Additionally, elderly people had more authority than children, further reinforcing the existing power differentials. Respondent shared on this

“I come from a Pathan background, and in our culture, there is some discrimination based on being a male or female. There are certain expectations and limitations placed on girls in my society”.

Another respondent said, “I have started the business after marriage because I am married and a married women gets liberty if the husband and in-laws are compromising”.

The above respondent expressed gratitude for her in law’s family who deviation from societal norms, which granted her the liberty to pursue personal interests and aspirations. The statement also suggests that the individual's perceived sense of freedom was influenced by her marital status. The author implies that married women were granted a certain degree of liberty when her husband and in-laws were willing to make compromises.

Women frequently experience a dual disadvantage because of their gender and their involvement in operating a small business. Due to the predominantly unstructured nature of the home-based business sector, women frequently engage in informal interactions. Specifically, within male-dominated structures such as wholesale markets and vendor systems. In-depth interviews with the respondents projected the significance of structural and cultural support required across all dimensions of the business channel. Respondent shared with resentment,

“Men are the biggest problem for women in business in Pakistan because they are in charge of everything.”

Gender influences business selection as well. Mostly, startups were employing their talent set, is highly influenced by Pakistan's nurturing practices. It the patriarchal attitude (Ahmet & Selcen, 2019), in which women in whatever role, i.e., daughter, sister, wife, and mother, were assigned to all sort of domestic responsibilities (Anzak & Sultana, 2020). The statistics demonstrated that most of the respondents in this study were active in entrepreneurship as a result of these skill sets that they had learned as a responsibility or hobbies in their early life. Gender segregation was another commonly prevailing norm in Pakistani culture (Azam Roomi & Harrison, 2010). Consequently, societal norms have given rise to a set of gender-based stereotypes regarding behavioural expectations (Xu, et al., 2018; Chinomona & Maziriri, 2015).

In short, the status of women is as subordinates and controlled in Pakistani society by men. They expected to seek permissions, which lowers their self-esteem and motivation. It also makes it difficult for women to succeed in business since they are not perceived as financial decision-makers or entrepreneurs. Being a woman in a patriarchal society and small business ownership creates challenging environment to prove themselves as capable beings.

4. Lack of Role Models:

The understanding that they required assistance and that creating a mentoring relationship may be a way to their achievement, was identified as a critical success factor

for these women. These entrepreneurs showed a sense of autonomy to approach potential mentors and form mentor connections. But at the early stage of their enterprise usually they fail to engage with the mentors and role models. Therefore, entering into the field which was dominated by the presence of the males, they had to struggle to identify the role models who were females and that was more significant when many of them enter with lacking any professional knowledge of entrepreneurship.

One of the Respondent during the focus group used the term “Gohree nayab” precious stones, found rarely but the possession makes them feel empowered and accomplished. During the field visits to the exhibitions and Gala events, it was found the many of the event participants were unenlightened about the presence of the successful role models in their region. Even when asked them about few names, they wished to help me network to them as they were new to the entrepreneurial landscape and extremely in need of such support. Mentoring was put forward as a strategy that these women could employ when faced with obstacles and challenges. Literature also supports this finding that many advantages were transferred through their presence and their invisibility adds to the challenges of the women entrepreneurs (Adler & Kwon, 2002; Chinomona & Maziriri, 2015) In accordance with Archuleta , it is more probable for women to experience adverse consequences because of these factors, which subsequently diminishes their inclination to engage in interdependent business ventures (Archuleta, 2015).

5. Poor Knowledge of Small Business Expansion:

Present research has identified that many women and students are pursuing their small-scale business alongside their jobs and education. While some of them were even only working on their entrepreneurial ventures so that they can contribute to the household income by generating revenues. But one significant feature that was revealed by the data analysis was that most of respondents had no proper knowledge of business plans and they were at times in a challenging situation to move on in their ventures.

Research showed that many entrepreneurs failed to expand or just cannot move on to the next point in the growth of their enterprises because of insufficient funds or financial resources. They overlook the advertising side of the entrepreneurship and invest all their funds in the purchase of the raw material, another hurdle mentioned was that that she was not making logs of the inputs and out puts and after a year when she had to show the growth of her business she could not make to the investors. So, what they had learnt was by asking the other entrepreneurs, by meeting in the chamber houses and by relating in the workshops and trainings. Many even were learning by doing and they had been paying high prices to that learning mechanism.

Financial resources through the formal and informal means were one of the limiting factors hence they worked for a long time at the startup level until they get some financial help from family or generate enough revenue from their small firms to take it to further expansion. The respondents said that she tried to get loan from the woman bank, but her credit history was problem where she dropped the idea of taking notes on bank.

6. Lack of Reliable Team Members and Networking Challenges:

The experience of being a woman in the entrepreneurial landscape presents unique challenges that go beyond the financial aspects of running a business. A significant challenge that was encountered by the respondents, was the difficulty of creating a dependable team. The process of finding suitable individuals extends beyond skill assessment; it encompasses identifying individuals who were genuine, had comprehension of and alignment with the work demanded. The limited availability of reliable team members had a strong influence on the output of the enterprise, highlighting the significance of establishing a community that aligns with the customers and enterprise values.

Networking, like any other field, comes with its own set of opportunities and challenges. Today, traditional market networks in Pakistan often create a sense of exclusivity and male dominance, making it challenging to establish meaningful connections (Azmi, 2017). In various circumstances, participants who were quite senior in terms of their work experiences, often shared that their voices being overshadowed, emphasising the importance of actively searching for and establishing environments where their narratives were acknowledged and shared. This challenge was creating a speed breaker to their growth in the larger context.

Resilience emerges as a crucial asset when confronted with these challenges. The absence of a dependable team and the challenges in networking should not be seen only as obstacles; rather, they present us with chances to lead and bring about change. By promoting a culture that values inclusivity and support in their businesses and networks, they were addressing the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs and create opportunities for future generations. The accounts of women entrepreneurs discussed in the above data, encompass more than mere accounts of hardship. They represent stories of overcoming challenges, demonstrating resilience amidst uncertainty (Karim, 2014), and showcasing the transformative potential of collective support in dismantling obstacles.

7. Customer's Behaviour and Keeping Up with the Network Building:

Another difficulty faced by female entrepreneurs, particularly those who were just starting out, was creating networks and locating consumers for their goods online. Low levels of computer literacy and a lack of connections with the outside world are contributing factors. To increase the number of followers on their social media profiles, they occasionally attempted to win over fictitious customers. Influencers could increase the page's reach, but this is simply a short-term gain, and as one respondent stated (Khan, Salamzadeh, Shah, & Hussain, 2020), it ultimately led to the conclusion that only organic clients could truly help their business.

It creates fierce rivalry among e-business owners to attract clients and brand loyalists. Women business owners who participated in this research told that they lose the trust of their clients (Abd Rani & Hashim, 2017; Ahmet & Selcen, 2019) if they ignore their questions or take longer than expected to respond to them. They were constantly involved in online activities because they were afraid of losing their consumers. This was because, after they had established a solid line of organic customers, abandoning them would be a significant loss of time and effort.

6. Conclusion

The research findings can be concluded that the socio-cultural context of these female entrepreneurs hinder their ability to fully pursue their firms. When these women face criticism from both the community and the household, the situation becomes considerably more challenging. According to the research findings, the community's belief that women are incapable of performing such tasks often hinders their economic participation and progress during the startup phase. These difficulties make it harder for them to survive and remain sustainable because their minor carelessness was not disregarded and was securitized by assigning them labels and effectively critiquing them.

Analysis of the field data reflects that these women entrepreneurs were faced with the challenged cultural context in terms of humiliation when they fail to submit the tasks in time (Butler, 2004; Ahmad, Rafiq, & Ahmad, 2018; Chant, 2016) or fail to address the family expectations but none of the respondent had shared that they were physically attacked. The findings of the research back up the claim that vulnerability and domestic violence are closely associated with women's economic empowerment. According to a study by Sarah Carter, 37% of the female survey participants were aware of instances in which female entrepreneurs faced humiliation or mockery. (Carter & Marlow, 2007).

Changing the existing social norms about women's work and the spaces where they can work would be difficult. Women entrepreneurs may face hurdles due to a variety of cultural issues in their society, economy, and politics, as well as other external events (Asiyanbola, 2005; Muhammad, Ximei, Saqib, & Beutell, 2021; Parveen & Junaid, 2019). However, struggle for these gender-based stereotypes will be less challenging when these women entrepreneurs get support from their families.

As a strategy they usually try to gain the support from their male family members so that they can lessen the associated risks while entering in the challenging men traditional roles of businessman. To pursue their ventures, they had to level the grounds at home first and gain the support from family particularly the male members. Most of them accounted for this practice, it will not only be helped them for comfortable working environment at home but also as a shield to protect from social cultural challenges like mobility to the markets, delivery of products, financial transactions handling. The respondents acknowledged the role and support of family was a significant contributor to their present-day success of business.

Present study found that contextual challenges were less problematic for those respondents who were able to gain some support from their families either emotional, managerial, or financial. They could plan for new experimentations required for the growth of their entrepreneurship because of this support and it ultimately leads to the sustainability of their business venture. So, the family support was seen as a one key factor by the women entrepreneurs to be accounted for their sustainable growth (Chinomona & Maziriri, 2015; Ahmet & Selcen, 2019). This support seeking behaviour can also be seen as an outcome of the cultural context and found important in other research findings of this region, where females are nurtured with the values of subordination to male in a patriarchal society (Maqbool, Parveen, & Yousuf, 2021). It was required, by the respondents for the number or

reasons and the most important aspect was the stress-free environment to focus on the entrepreneurship for creativity.

This study aimed to thoroughly address the issues raised by previous research and use this thorough knowledge to investigate how these issues affect Pakistani women's participation in business and entrepreneurship. Insufficient training and education in entrepreneurial work, limited financial resources, low levels of digital literacy, legal restrictions, cultural limitations, a lack of social support, and difficulties striking a work-life balance are the main consequences, as previously identified. As a result, the current study provides fresh insights into the ideas of sustainability and growth of women entrepreneurship in Pakistan, as well as how to handle unexpectedly difficult situations, within the social capital literature.

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